

1 **m6A RNA-sequencing in HIV1+ cells.**

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6 We demonstrate here activation of cellular nuclear transport as measured by m6A-sequencing in HIV-1
7 infected cells. Component genes of the m6A transcriptome in HIV-1+ cells included export factors *Alyref*
8 and *Nxf1*.

9 Citations

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